

HORIZON-RIA

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01 GA-101084344

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-09

Grant Agreement: 101084344

WHEATBIOME

Unraveling the potential of the wheat microbiome for the development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient wheat-derived food & feed products

DELIVERABLE D7.7 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS – BATCH 1

Document ID: WHEATBIOME-WP7-D7.7-PU-v.1.4

Due date of deliverable: 31/03/2024

Dissemination Level	
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PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
SEN	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Task leader partner for this deliverable: EDAGRI

Document status and versions		
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Version	Date	Description
1.1	15-03-2024	First version
1.2	20-03-2024	Second version
1.3	22-03-2024	Third version
1.4	25-03-2024	Correction and relocation of concepts

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the proposed actions and activities for developing and implementing all communication and dissemination materials pertaining to the practice abstracts (PA) within the WHEATBIOME framework. A strategy plan will be developed to effectively make use of the projects results across scientific, food industry and economic routes transforming WHEATBIOME outcomes into concrete value and impact for society. Indeed, the practice abstracts herein defined are described as a valuable tool to provide a bridge between theoretical knowledge raised from WHEATBIOME to its practical application, offering tangible guidance, solutions, or recommendations that can be directly implemented or integrated into professional practice. As the significance of microbial communities in shaping the resilience of future food systems continues to garner attention, there remains a gap in practical knowledge concerning the roles of various stakeholders within the food chain, including farmers and the food industry. The insights gained from WHEATBIOME can offer valuable guidance: farmers can utilize specific wheat varieties tailored to agronomic and environmental conditions, enhancing wheat quality while minimizing immunogenicity. Similarly, the food industry stands to benefit from leveraging this knowledge to develop novel, microbial-based foods with superior nutritional profiles, while also strategizing on the repurposing of byproducts for feed applications.

Different activities are intended to be organized as practical abstracts. Those practical abstracts are aligned to reach the main food chain actors (farmers, food industries, farming associations, research and health specialists and/or consumers). The practical abstracts will be organized in two well differentiated groups, the pre-results and post results. The pre-results will be activities focused on attracting interest in food system-related actors, giving information about the main objectives of WHEATBIOME, highlighting the main challenges and open communication between the actors and the project. In a further step, after data was collected, several post-results activities will be organized to show the main results found within the different Work Package (WP).

Regarding the pre-results content, workshops tailored for wheat farmers under PA1 and PA2 will be organized. These sessions will serve as a platform to demonstrate the invaluable opportunities and benefits realized throughout the project's duration and beyond and will be based mainly on WP1 and 2. While conducted in-person in Spain,

they will be virtually accessible to our partners worldwide, ensuring comprehensive participation and knowledge dissemination. These workshops underscore the pivotal role of farmer education and engagement in maximizing project impact and fostering sustainable agricultural practices. Additionally, an open webinar will be organized under the framework of WP5. The PA3 will be oriented to chicken farmers and overall feed industry. Likewise, another webinar will be organized focused on WP3 and WP4, under the PA4 and oriented to the food industry. Several press releases (of approximately 400 words) will also be made with the results of the study of media in the food sector, from farmers to consumers. Several articles will be published (of approximately 2000 words) in open-access technical magazines as “Agricultura” with 8000 issues and “Ganadería” with 6000 issues, including paper and digital formats, and it is expected also around 5000 views of the workshop information in social network. Once the final data from the studies are obtained (post –result content) the same type of events will be carried out to be able to complete dissemination. Also, five video documentaries, one dedicated to every PA (approximately three or four minutes long) will be designed as an educational campaign, to explain the WHEATBIOME’s findings to the food chain and end consumers.

The practice abstracts of WHEATBIOME reflect briefly the different problems, purposes, theoretical frameworks, methodology, results and conclusions of the project. On the other hand, the way in which each target audience is reached will be proposed, with an estimate of reach and how they can respond to the information and the practical applications that can be given to it will be analyzed.

The selected practice abstracts are:

- PA1-Dry farming and irrigation impact on nutritional quality of wheat and impact in food industry applications
- PA2-The practice of ecological vs conventional techniques on wheat microbiomes and attributes. Selection of wheat varieties depending on whether conditions and agricultural practices.
- PA3-New formulation for poultry feed via fermentation by means of recircularization.
- PA4-Identify benefits of innovative fermented food and feed products.
- PA5-Impact of agricultural practices on the immunogenic potential of wheat and human health

2. TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2. TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	5
3. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	6
4. INTRODUCTION	7
5. PRACTICE ABSTRACTS	7
5.1. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 1	7
5.1.1. SHORT SUMMARY OF PA1	7
5.2. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 2	8
5.2.1. SHORT SUMMARY OF PA2	8
5.3. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 3	9
5.3.1. SHORT SUMMARY OF PA3	10
5.4. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 4	10
5.4.1. SHORT SUMMARY OF PA4	10
5.5. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 5	10
5.5.1. SHORT SUMMARY OF PA5	11
6. ACTIVITIES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF PRACTICE ABSTRACTS AND EXPECTED OUTCOMES.....	11
6.1. PRE-RESULTS	11
6.1.1. PA1 - DRY FARMING AND IRRIGATION IMPACT ON NUTRITIONAL QUALITY OF WHEAT AND IMPACT IN FOOD INDUSTRY APPLICATIONS	11
6.1.2. PA2 - THE PRACTICE OF ECOLOGICAL VS CONVENTIONAL TECHNIQUES ON WHEAT MICROBIOMES AND ATTRIBUTES. SELECTION OF WHEAT VARIETIES DEPENDING ON WHETHER CONDITIONS AND AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES.....	13
6.1.3. PA3 - NEW FORMULATION FOR POULTRY FEED VIA FERMENTATION BY MEANS OF RECIRCULARIZATION.....	14
6.1.4. PA4 - IDENTIFY BENEFITS OF INNOVATIVE FERMENTED FOOD AND FEED PRODUCTS.....	15
6.1.5. PA5 - IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES ON THE IMMUNOGENIC POTENTIAL OF WHEAT AND HUMAN HEALTH.....	16
6.2. POST- RESULTS	17
7. CONCLUSIONS	18
8. ANNEXES.....	19

3. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

PA: Practice Abstract

WP: Work Package

4. INTRODUCTION

The challenges confronting wheat farmers, such as water scarcity and narrow profit margins, underscore the importance of providing training to various stakeholders within the food system. To address these issues effectively, a range of topics will be explored, aimed at fostering alternative approaches to wheat cultivation. This inclusive approach ensures the involvement of farmers, industry players, scientific communities, and end consumers alike. By equipping all actors with relevant knowledge and skills, WHEATBIOME can contribute to collectively work towards innovative solutions that benefit the entire food system, from soil to plate.

5. PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

5.1. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 1

The first practice abstract aims to provide farmers and related industries with comprehensive knowledge on how “Dry farming and irrigation impact on nutritional quality of wheat and impact in food industry applications”. This is a relevant topic to address among local farmers due to its effect on water availability and their commercial margins, as well as in the industry due to the new opportunities that may arise in the production of high value-added products.

The consumer is also involved, since as a final decision in the purchase of food he prescribes the decisions to be made.

5.1.1.SHORT SUMMARY OF PA1

Wheat produced under dry conditions is expected to have significantly different characteristics from that produced under irrigation. Hydric stress profoundly impacts plant metabolism, disrupting key processes such as photosynthesis, stomatal regulation, osmotic adjustment, and metabolite accumulation. Under this scenario, the nutritional quality of wheat which depends on the number of proteins, lipids, carbohydrates and micronutrients will be affected. Additionally, specific metabolites involved in stress tolerance and defense mechanisms, such as phenolic compounds or carotenoids can appear highly accumulated under water stress. Indeed, it is possible that different qualities of wheat can be established based on whether it has been irrigated or not, and

therefore that the members of the food chain establish remuneration according to these qualities. Furthermore, the plant and soil microbiota can be directly correlated with the hydric conditions affecting the overall plant and soil health status. This fact would be interesting for farmers in areas where dry land was the only viable option, since it would allow them to differentiate themselves and be environmentally but also economically sustainable. Access to accurate and timely information on water stress is essential for farmers to make informed decisions, adapt to changing environmental conditions, and ensure the long-term sustainability of agricultural practices. The farmers will be the main target public to PA1. Likewise, farmer suppliers play a crucial role in supplying raw materials to the food industry. Certainly, the food industry can choose farmer suppliers who not only provide raw materials but also contribute to sustainable, reliable, and mutually beneficial partnerships. WHEATBIOME knowledge can highlight valuable information not only to farmers but also to industries in order to offer foods that the consumer sees as different, with greater acceptance and values such as sustainability that are appreciated by more and more groups in society.

5.2. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 2

The second PA aims to provide farmers and related industries with a comprehensive view on how using organic or conventional production of wheat crops affects the soil in which it is grown and how it will lead to a significant effect on the nutritional quality of the grain and in the applications it will have in the food industry.

This is a relevant topic to address among local farmers because of the effect that agriculture has on the soil and its ecosystems. Preserving their fertility and being able to differentiate their products could increase the commercial margins of producers, as is already the case with organic farming. Furthermore, new opportunities may arise for the processing industry in the production of high added value products.

The consumer, being the final decision-maker in the purchase of food, is also involved in the decisions to be made.

5.2.1.SHORT SUMMARY OF PA2

Wheat produced under rainfed conditions is commonly expected to have significantly different characteristics from that produced under irrigated land due to the effect of

diluted substances in the irrigation water. But this is not the only reason: water stress can impact the primary plant metabolism, influencing the nutritional quality (expression of micro and macronutrients) as well as affecting the secondary metabolism, and therefore the expression of bioactive compounds such as carotenoids or phenolic compounds. Moreover, WHEATBIOME aims to understand if the hydric stress may affect the expression of immunogenic proteins unveiling how water conditions can impact the wheat gluten at qualitative and quantitative points of view.

It is also possible that different qualities of wheat can be established based on whether it has been irrigated or not, and therefore that the members of the food chain establish remuneration according to these qualities. This fact would be interesting for farmers in areas where rainfed farming was the only viable option, since, in positive terms, it would allow them to differentiate themselves and be environmentally but also economically sustainable. But we also need to have into account that irrigation can affect the ecology and function of microbial communities which can be key in the sustainable development of agriculture.

Industries can offer foods that the consumer sees as different, with greater acceptance and values such as sustainability that are appreciated by more and more groups in society.

5.3. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 3

The third PA aims to provide poultry farmers and feed mills with information on how by-products from fermented wheat intended for human consumption can fit into their animals' rations.

The use of raw materials based on the circular economy has a long history in the sector, and the sustainability values of these raw materials, together with their greater digestibility, could make them interesting for formulators. We also need to have one important thing into account: it is expected that feed rich in prebiotics and probiotics can impact the animal health and wellbeing, affecting the production of animal food.

The consumer is also involved, since as the final decision-maker in the purchase of food, he values that the impact of foods of animal origin has the smallest possible environmental footprint and the higher standards of animal welfare as possible.

5.3.1.SHORT SUMMARY OF PA3

By-products from the fermented wheat beverage production industry can be an interesting alternative to enter into food rations for chickens.

They are raw materials that are very assimilable by animals, and at the same time, their use in the manufacture of feed reduces the environmental footprint of livestock production. Their use could also provide the livestock sector with tools that improve livestock nutrition, highlighting respect for the environment and perhaps therefore have the possibility of obtaining poultry meat with differential value in the market.

5.4. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 4

The fourth PA aims to highlight the fermentation of wheat products throughout the food chain, due to its importance in obtaining healthy foods as well as opening the possibility of obtaining "different" foods for the consumer.

5.4.1.SHORT SUMMARY OF PA4

Fermented foods from herbaceous crops, such as wheat, can be an increasing value in human nutrition due to their healthy properties.

This is an issue of crucial importance both for farmers, who will see how their production is dedicated to higher-value foods, and for industries that will have a greater repertoire of healthy products to offer, with which both groups are expected to have an economic return positive.

The consumer is also key player because of the health-related values that these foods provide and that could influence their purchasing decision.

5.5. PRACTICE ABSTRACT 5

The fifth PA aims to link the agricultural production models of wheat cultivation and its impact on the quantity and quality of wheat gluten, and therefore the products made with it.

5.5.1.SHORT SUMMARY OF PA5

Nowadays immune reactions to gluten are an increasingly common problem in our society. Linking wheat production models with the final gluten parameters seems key to the food chain and its importance can be seen throughout it, from the consumer, backwards, all the way to the farmer.

Understanding how wheat varieties and agronomic or environment conditions can impact the immunogenic proteins profile as a valuable way could help not to remove the gluten in the wheat products, as it is a necessary substance.

On the part of the farmer, knowing what practices are appropriate to produce better-accepted gluten foods will make the farming business more profitable.

6. ACTIVITIES FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF PRACTICE ABSTRACTS AND EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The dissemination activities will be organized into two blocks, one pre-results and the other after the results are obtained. Both will be aimed at different groups including producers, industry representatives, researchers, health professionals and consumers. Problems, guidelines, and possible conclusions that can be glimpsed will be established. The main difference is not only the accuracy of data supplied in them, but also the videos with the conclusions for every PA that will be prepared after the results have been obtained.

6.1. PRE-RESULTS

6.1.1. PA1 - Dry farming and irrigation impact on nutritional quality of wheat and impact in food industry applications

The basis of this dissemination will set on a round table in a dedicated workshop organized by EDIAGRI, that will be organized near the province where the farmers who collaborate in WP1 are placed so that they are even more involved with WHEATBIOME project. This workshop will have an estimated face-to-face capacity of 80 people representing different groups. After, the workshop will also be available on the YouTube channel on which it is hosted, expecting to reach a wider audience in the following months.

Attendees of the workshop will receive a digital flyer and their registration will involve receiving a biannual digital newsletter with project updating.

The specific dissemination of the information and expected outcomes for each group is described as follows:

a) Farmers and cereal industry

A press release will be sent to specialized media so that they can echo the conclusions and balance of the workshop and a technical article will also be prepared that will be published in both paper and digital format of "Agriculture", the EDAGRI magazine. The group's social networks will broadcast live the different presentations. Around 400 people (farmers and industrial workers) are expected to attend the workshop, in person or by watching the Youtube video. On the other hand, "Agricoltura" magazine has got a total print-run of 8000 issues, including paper and digital formats, and it is expected also to reach around 5000 views of the workshop information in social network.

Outcomes: The information supplied in PA1 could help farmers to be aware of how water availability affects their activities, their future and their commercial margins, as well as industries could find new opportunities that might arise in the production of high value-added products.

b) Researchers

Entities participating in research projects related to wheat cultivation will be invited to the workshop (around 10 in total), in order to increase networking and synergies in research on the subject.

Outcomes: These connections could help them with guidelines that other similar projects could have developed previously and find better options for their future research.

c) Consumers

A press release with a friendlier approach will be sent to the general media so that they can be echoed in their spaces dedicated to the final consumer. It is expected that around 30 general media will receive this info.

Outcomes: This information will make the consumers aware of how their purchasing decisions affect the environment and how research is addressing new opportunities for more sustainable food.

6.1.2. PA2 - The practice of ecological vs conventional techniques on wheat microbiomes and attributes. Selection of wheat varieties depending on whether conditions and agricultural practices.

The basis of this dissemination will be a round table in a workshop shared with PA1, as they focus the same target and joining both will optimize the dissemination. Technical data were previously shown in PA1.

Attendees will receive a digital flyer and their registration will involve receiving a biannual digital newsletter updating the Project.

The specific dissemination of the information will be carried out by groups as follows:

a) Farmers and cereal industry

As in PA1, a press release of the workshop will be sent to specialized media so that they can echo the conclusions and balance. A technical article will also be prepared in "Agricultura", the EDAGRI magazine. The group's social networks will support the dissemination of the event. The expected attendance are 400 people (farmers and industrial workers). Also, an article in "Agricultura" magazine will be published.

Outcomes: The information supplied in PA2 could help farmers to realize that the fertility of the soil is essential for their crop productivity, and microbiomes are key to reaching it. Choosing different wheat varieties according to these new criteria will be an option. Differentiating their products according to this could also increase commercial margins for the whole food chain, as the developed products would match new requirements from the market.

b) Researchers

Entities participating in research projects related to wheat cultivation will be invited to the workshop (around 10 in total), in order to increase networking and synergies in research on the subject.

Outcomes: These connections could help them with guidelines that other similar projects could have developed previously and find better options for their coming research.

c) Consumers

A press release with a friendlier approach will be sent to the general media so that they can be echoed in their spaces dedicated to the final consumer.

Outcomes: This will make them aware of how their purchasing decisions affect the environment and could open new opportunities for more sustainable food.

It is expected that around 30 general media will receive this info.

6.1.3. PA3-New formulation for poultry feed via fermentation by means of recircularization.

The basis of this dissemination will be a webinar dedicated to poultry farmers and feed industries.

This webinar will have an online estimated audience of 60 people representing these groups, but which will be expanded up to 400 visits in the following months thanks to the streaming and viewing broadcast on the YouTube channel on which it is hosted.

The attendees will receive a digital flyer and their registration will involve receiving a biannual digital newsletter updating the Project.

The specific dissemination of the information will be carried out by groups as follows:

a) Chicken farmers and feed industries

A press release will be sent to specialized media so that they can echo the conclusions and balance of the workshop and a technical article will also be prepared that will be published in the paper and digital format of "Ganaderia", the EDAGRI magazine. The group's social networks will broadcast live the different presentations.

Around 400 people (farmers and industrial workers) are expected to attend the webinar, directly or watching the Youtube video. On the other hand, "Ganaderia" magazine has got a total print-run of 6000 issues, including paper and digital formats, and it is expected also around 5000 views of the workshop information in social network.

Outcomes: The information supplied in PA3 could provide poultry farmers and feed mills with information on how by-products from fermented wheat intended for human consumption can fit into their animals' rations. Higher digestibility of these new raw materials is expected to have incidence in animal welfare and sustainability of chicken production.

b) Researchers

Entities participating in research projects related to feed production will be invited to the workshop (around 3 in total), in order to increase networking and synergies in research on the subject.

Outcomes: These connections are expected to help them with guidelines that other similar projects could have developed previously and find better options for their coming research.

c) Consumers

A press release with a friendlier approach will be sent to the general media so that they can be echoed in their spaces dedicated to the final consumer.

Outcomes: This will make them aware of how their purchasing decisions affect the environment and could open new opportunities for more sustainable food. It is expected that around 30 general media will receive this info.

6.1.4. PA4 - Identify benefits of innovative fermented food and feed products.

The basis of this dissemination will be a webinar dedicated to wheat farmers and food industries. This webinar will have an online estimated audience of 60 people representing these groups, but which will be expanded up to 400 visits in the following months thanks to the streaming and viewing broadcast on the YouTube channel on which it is hosted. Attendees will receive a digital flyer and their registration will involve receiving a biannual digital newsletter with project updating.

The specific dissemination of the information will be carried out by groups as follows:

a) Wheat farmers and food industries

A press release will be sent to specialized media so that they can echo the conclusions and balance of the webinar and a technical article will also be prepared that will be published in the paper and digital format of "Agricultura", the EDAGRI magazine. The group's social networks will broadcast live the different presentations.

Around 400 people (farmers and industrial workers) are expected to attend the webinar, directly or watching the Youtube video. On the other hand, "Agricultura" magazine has got a total print-run of 8000 issues, including paper and digital, and it is expected also around 5000 views of the workshop information in social network.

Outcomes: The information supplied in PA4 could provide wheat farmers with information related on how their production could be dedicated to higher-value foods, and for industries that will have a greater repertoire of healthy products to offer; both groups are expected to have an economic return positive.

b) Researchers

Entities participating in research projects related to feed production will be invited to the workshop (around 3 in total), in order to increase networking and synergies in research on the subject.

Outcomes: These connections could help them with guidelines that other similar projects could have developed previously and find better options for their coming research

c) Consumers

A press release with a friendlier approach will be sent to the general media so that they can be echoed in their spaces dedicated to the final consumer. It is expected that around 30 general media will receive this info.

Outcomes: This information will make them aware of health-related values linked to these new food and could positively impact their purchase habits.

6.1.5. PA5 - Impact of agricultural practices on the immunogenic potential of wheat and human health

The basis of this dissemination will be a webinar dedicated mainly to wheat farmers and health professionals. Researchers and consumers will be an important part of it too.

This webinar will have an online estimated audience of 60 people representing these groups, but which will be expanded up to 400 visits in the following months thanks to the streaming and viewing broadcast on the YouTube channel on which it is hosted.

Attendees will receive a digital flyer and their registration will involve receiving a biannual digital newsletter updating the project.

The specific dissemination of the information will be carried out by groups as follows:

a) Wheat farmers

A press release will be sent to specialized media so that they can echo the conclusions and balance of the webinar and a technical article will also be prepared that will be published in the paper and digital format of "Agricultura", the EDAGRI magazine. The group's social networks will broadcast live the different presentations. Around 400 farmers are expected to attend the webinar, directly or watching the Youtube video. On the other hand, "Agricultura" magazine has got a total print-run of 8000 issues, including paper and digital, and it is expected also around 5000 views of the workshop info in social network

Outcomes: The information supplied in PA5 may help farmers to decide what farming practices are appropriate to produce better-accepted gluten foods will make his business more profitable

b) Researchers

Entities participating in research projects related to wheat and immunogenic proteins will be invited to the webinar (around 2 in total), in order to increase networking and synergies in research on the subject.

Outcomes: These connections could help them with guidelines that other similar projects could have developed previously and find better options for their coming research

c) Health professionals

The webinar will be attended by 1-2 health professionals who can give their vision and advice on the effect of gluten on human nutrition. A press release with a health approach will be sent to the specialized health media so that they can be echoed in their spaces. It is expected that around 5 health-related media will receive this info.

Outcomes: Their presence in the webinar will allow a better dissemination of information in specialized health media and will make other health professionals aware of the importance of agriculture in food and gluten (perhaps an issue not so well known in their community).

d) Consumers

A press release with a friendlier approach will be sent to the general media so that they can be echoed in their spaces dedicated to the final consumer. It is expected that around 30 general media will receive this info.

Outcomes: This information will make them aware of agricultural and health-related values are linked through gluten and could create new purchase habits.

6.2. POST- RESULTS

The post-results dissemination has the same structure as the previously reflected for pre-results dissemination. There will be a workshop shared between PA1 and PA2, webinars for PA3, PA4 and PA5. Digital flyers will be sent for the attendants. There will be technical and general press releases and a, technical article and social network for every PA.

The main difference to the pre-results dissemination is that dissemination of post-results will include short videos (with 2-3 minutes), as a balance about every PA. They will be

uploaded to EDAGRI YouTube and further shared within WHEATBIOME webpage and social media channels (including LinkedIn and X).

7. CONCLUSIONS

The landscape of wheat production in Spain is undergoing a significant transformation. Factors such as the limitation of irrigation water or the environmental constraints reflected in European regulations are challenges that, on the other hand, open up opportunities for research. This applied research leads to new and more sustainable techniques and processes in agriculture and allows, for example, the emergence of raw materials for the food and feed industry. Also, the production of high-nutritional-level foods that address people's health-related needs.

Consumers awareness about consuming sustainable and healthy foods is increasing. However, wheat consumption is being affected by the rise of immune reactions to food related to gluten intake. Among them, celiac disease remains a significant health concern due to its prevalence, health impacts, diagnostic challenges, impact on dietary trends, and ongoing research efforts aimed at better understanding and managing the condition. Increased awareness, early detection, and access to gluten-free options are essential in improving the quality of life for individuals living with celiac disease. Likewise, is important to give tools to farmers, food industry and consumers in order to understand how the food processing from the soil, where the food begun, can impact the immunogenicity, bioactivities and nutritional quality of food and feed products.

Properly identifying the target audiences of the practice abstracts and sending them a multi-support message will be a key factor in advancing these new developments.

The optimal dissemination of the research is the proper way for the results to be known and used by the different stakeholders of the wheat-related food chain.

By fostering broad engagement with these results, WHEATBIOME can drive the way to farmers adopt more sustainable practices and also support the progress towards a more sustainable and equitable future in wheat production in Spain.

8. ANNEXES

Annex 1: Communication and dissemination activities for PA1 and PA2

Annex 2: Communication and dissemination activities for PA3 and PA4

Annex 3: Communication and dissemination activities for PA5

